

The Effect of Knowledge Sharing and Knowledge Management on Member Competence and its Impact on Member Performance: Study in Kodam Iskandar Muda

¹Teguh Arief Indratmoko, Nasir, Said Musnadi

Department of Management, Universitas Syiah Kuala, Indonesia

Abstract: This study is to test the effect of knowledge sharing and knowledge management on member competencies and its impact on member performance. The object of this research is Kodam Iskandar Muda, located in Aceh Province, Indonesia. The population is its member (employee) as much as 297 people. The sample is taken using census method, so the amount is also 297 people as respondents. The verification of causality test uses structural equation modeling (SEM). The indirect effect is tested using Sobel test. The result shows that knowledge sharing effects member performance significantly, knowledge management effects member performance significantly, knowledge sharing effects member competence significantly, knowledge management effects member competencies significantly, member competence effects member performance significantly, knowledge sharing does not effect member performance through member competence, and knowledge management does not effect member performance through member competence. These findings support the realm of science that prove the causality theories. The originality rests in the collaboration of the previous models, and in using SEM as a statistical approach to test the effect among variables. The limitation resides in the number of variables and object. These results also impact to the practical leaders especially in the Kodam Iskandar Muda as an object.

Keyword: Knowledge Sharing, Knowledge Management, Member Competence and Member Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Every human being has the potential to act in various forms of activity. The ability to act can be obtained by humans either naturally (present from birth) or learned. Although humans have the potential to behave in certain ways, but that behavior is only actualized at certain times. The potential for certain behaviors is called ability, whereas the expression of this process is known as performance. Employee performance is the result of work or work produced by each employee to assist business entities in achieving and realizing business entity goals. Basically, the performance of a person is individual because each employee has a different level of ability. A person's performance depends on a combination of ability, effort, and opportunity obtained (Timpe, 2002).

In an organization, the existence of human resources plays a very important role to achieve the goals of an organization. Iskandar Muda Regional Military Command (often abbreviated as Kodam Iskandar Muda or Kodam IM), formerly known as Regional Military Command I / Iskandar Muda, is a Regional Defense Command covering the Province of Aceh, Indonesia. Human resources owned by the Kodam Iskandar Muda organization are one of the main factors for the development of the organization to be better, especially in providing services to the community in accordance with the main task of the Kodam Iskandar Muda, so that efforts to improve human resources are the main strategies in achieving competition which increasingly tightened by this globalization. Given that the organization is a social unit that is consciously coordinated with a reactive boundary that can be identified, work continuously to achieve a common goal (Robbins and Judge, 2012).

Furthermore, the performance of Kodam Iskandar Muda members will achieve maximum results if supported by their knowledge sharing. Each member is expected to continue to explore their knowledge and not just depend on or fixate on the existing system. So it can be said that each member of the organization has a role in improving the progress of the organization. Each member of the Kodam Iskandar Muda must focus on increasing individual knowledge gained from daily experience, knowledge that can be transformed between individuals so that it is easier to describe in documents,

practices, training and others where the authors categorize them in the form of work procedures and technology, skills members and creating good attitudes among their members so that they work with high performance, quality and with a large quantity of work. This will lead to the progress of the Kodam Iskandar Muda .

If we depart from the phenomenon of the performance of members of the Indonesian Military Command, it seems that the performance is still low. This can be seen from the implementation of the information technology service program at the Kodam Iskandar Muda, that is the Information Technology System Program (ITSP) management still needs an improvement. So there is a need of knowledge sharing and knowledge management, to provide services to the community.

In order to improve member performance, knowledge sharing is needed, that is, the knowledge possessed by members which is inherent in each member, such as members' confidence in the organization, values shared by members, work experience, and knowledge in themselves. - each member. Research conducted by (Susanto, Faisal and Putra, 2019) where the results of knowledge management research, organizational learning, job satisfaction, organizational commitment and employee performance have gone well, knowledge management, organizational learning and job satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on employee organizational commitment. Knowledge sharing has a role in creating higher knowledge that has to do with the work of each member in the Kodam Iskandar Muda area. Given the importance of knowledge sharing consisting of various activities of members to share information with other members, there is a need to form the behavior of each member in a variety of information that is suitable for colleagues from various organizational units outside the Kodam Iskandar Muda .

Knowledge sharing has an important role to enhance the ability of each individual in the organization, because through knowledge sharing, knowledge that is both tacit and explicit can be disseminated, implemented and developed. (Trivellas *et al.*, 2015) revealed that a culture of knowledge sharing can develop new general abilities in individuals or sharpen the level of competencies that already exist in themselves, such as creating new ideas in carrying out tasks, being able to communicate well, maintaining relationships between members (interpersonal), able to prioritize various things, increase creativity, make plans, and are able to solve problems, and teamwork.

One of the factors that can influence the performance of Kodam IM members is the competency of the members. Research conducted by (Azmi, Nasir and Sofyan, 2019) proves that employee competence has an influence in improving employee performance. Then research (Salda, Faisal and Majid, 2019) proved that teacher competence has an influence in improving teacher performance. Competence is an ability to carry out or do a job or task based on knowledge and skills. The problem faced by members of the Kodam IM regarding competence is that there are still many members who do not yet have competencies in accordance with their main tasks and functions so that the expected performance achievements are not achieved in line with expectations.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Member Performance

The success of an organization is influenced by the performance (job performance) of employees, for that every company will try to improve the performance of employees in achieving organizational goals that have been set. Organizational culture that grows and is well maintained will be able to spur the organization towards better development. On the other hand, the ability of leaders to move and empower employees will affect performance.

Employee performance refers to a person's achievements as measured by the standards and criteria set by the company. Management to achieve high human resource performance is intended to improve the company as a whole (Flippo, 1997). According to (Waldman and Siegel, 2008) performance is a combination of behavior with achievement of what is expected and the choice or part of the conditions of the task that exist in each individual in the organization. Meanwhile, according to (Mangkunegara, 2010) performance is the result of work in quality and quantity that can be achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. (Suprihanto, 1987) said that performance is the result of an employee's work during a certain period compared to various possibilities, for example standards, targets / criteria that have been determined in advance and have been mutually agreed upon.

Employee performance refers to a person's achievements as measured by standards and criteria set by the company. Management to achieve high human resource performance is intended to improve the company as a whole (Flippo, 1997). According to (Waldman and Siegel, 2008) performance is a combination of behavior with achievement of what is expected and the choice or part of the conditions of the task that exist in each individual in the organization. Meanwhile, according to (Mangkunegara, 2010) performance can be defined as work results in quality and quantity that can be achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks in accordance with the responsibilities given to him.

Member Competence

Individual competence in a simple sense is a combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes. Things where every individual who occupies a certain position, must have the required competencies, to match the desired results.

According to (Wibowo, 2016) "said that every organization was formed to achieve certain goals and if achieved then can be called a success". To achieve success, a strong foundation is needed in the form of: leadership competence, employee competence and work discipline that can strengthen and maximize competence. Competencies become very useful to help organizations create a culture of high performance, work performance in every process of human resources, employee selection, performance management, planning and so on.

According to (Hartati, 2005), "competence is the ability to carry out tasks in accordance with science and skills as well as technology and experience relevant to the task field so as to develop work motivation concerned and improve performance".

Along with the increasingly intense competition in the business world as a result of economic liberalization in various industrial sectors today, the role of human resources as the main determining factor of whether a company is able to compete dynamically and profitably is increasingly felt its importance. The competitive advantage of an organization is largely determined by the quality of its human resources. HR management must be carried out thoroughly within the framework of a strategic, integrated, interrelated and unity HR management system. Organizations really need competent human resources, have certain competencies needed to support the successful implementation of their work.

Knowledge Sharing

Knowledge sharing has an important role in increasing individual competence in organizations, because through knowledge sharing, tacit and explicit knowledge can be disseminated, implemented, and developed. (Trivellas *et al.*, 2015) revealed that the culture of knowledge sharing can develop new general competencies in individuals or sharpen existing competencies, such as creating new ideas, communicating, interpersonal relationships, prioritizing things, creativity, planning, problem solving, and team working. Management problems that often occur precisely because of lack of information needed by employees to carry out their duties. The application of knowledge sharing is expected to meet the information and knowledge needs of employees in order to carry out their duties properly.

Knowledge sharing is then directed at improving employee performance through individual competencies such as making decisions in problem solving. Research conducted by (Diana, 2009) revealed that knowledge sharing has a significant effect on employee performance. On the other hand, research conducted by (Yazhou and Jian, 2013) shows that knowledge sharing has no direct effect on employee performance, but is mediated by the variable innovation capability and intellectual capital. Based on the description there are differences in the results of research into gaps that will be examined in this study.

The relationship between knowledge and individual competencies of employees is also very important for employee performance in an organization. Over the past several decades, individual competencies have often been used for the basis of employee performance appraisal (Davidson and Voss, 2002). Competence as a measurement tool, identify behavioral factors related to performance in work and see how work is done. Research conducted by (Davidson and Voss, 2002) revealed that individual competencies had a significant effect on individual performance. Both of these variables have a positive effect, meaning that when individual competencies increase, it will increase individual performance as well, and vice versa..

Knowledge Management

Knowledge is increasingly being recognized as an important asset of the organization. The most recent paradigm is that knowledge is power. In a modern economy, organizations that utilize knowledge are organizations that have a competitive advantage. These competitive advantages are realized through the full use of information and data combined with utilizing the skills, ideas, commitment and motivation of employees. The new paradigm today is that knowledge in organizations must be shared in order to support the growth and development of organizations (Wijayanto and Kismono, 2004). There are two types of knowledge, namely (1) Implicit knowledge (tacit), which is knowledge that is still in the mind of individuals who have that knowledge and are personal in nature. Meanwhile, it is important for an organization to find, disseminate and utilize the implicit knowledge of each employee in order to optimize the use of his own intellectual capital. (2) Explicit knowledge is knowledge that is explicitly available in the organization. In general, explicit knowledge is structured and reflected in various references to regulations and work standards in organizations.

The difference between tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge suggests 4 basic patterns for creating knowledge in (Wijayanto and Kismono, 2004) organizations. (1) Socialization (from tacit to tacit), (2) Externalization (from tacit to explicit), (3) Combination from explicit to explicit and (4) Internalization from explicit to tacit.

Many definitions of knowledge management from various researchers. Each gave an interpretation based on professional background and research objectives. This study refers to (Mahfud, 2016) who suggested the main processes in knowledge management include the creation of knowledge (creation), the use of knowledge (utilization) and knowledge sharing (sharing). Knowledge creation is an activity to create knowledge. Knowledge can be obtained from information in the form of individual experience and expertise. Knowledge utilization is an activity related to the application of knowledge in the form of technical tools including machinery and equipment used to increase added value or productivity. Knowledge sharing involves the transfer of knowledge from one party to another. Sharing knowledge means that each individual is aware of the importance of knowledge for the company and shares knowledge gained with other individuals.

Research Hypothesis

From the discussion above, authors formulate the hypothesis research as follows.

H1 : The result shows that knowledge sharing effects member performance significantly,

H2 : knowledge management effects member performance significantly,

H3 : knowledge sharing effects member competence significantly,

H4 : knowledge management effects member competencies significantly,

H5 : member competence effects member performance significantly.

H6 : knowledge sharing effects member performance through member competence,

H7 : knowledge management effects member performance through member competence.

RESEARCH METHOD

The object of this research is the Kodam Iskandar Muda that is located in Aceh. The population is 297 people and the sample is taken with census method, that takes all population member. So that is as much as 297 people become respondents. Authors determine the constructs in measuring each variables, that are : 1) knowledge sharing : knowledge from coworkers, personal knowledge from seniors, share knowledge, share lessons, share reports and documents, share procedures, share rules in the work environment, and share instructions; 2) knowledge management : the use of knowledge, share knowledge, reflections on knowledge, and identification of knowledge; 3) member competence : level of knowledge, ability to work, communication skills, skills, mastery of it, and togetherness attitude; and 4) member performance : quality of work, work quantity, timeliness, time effectiveness, independence, and work commitment.

After collecting data, the next step is to analyze the data using SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) using the version 19 of the AMOS (Analysis of Moment Structure) program package and SPSS (Statistical Program for Social Sciences) version 22.0. The use of SEM allows researchers to examine the relationships between complex variables to get an overall picture of the whole model. According to (F. Hair Jr *et al.*, 2014) SEM method is a development of path analysis and multiple regression which are both a form of multivariate analysis.

By analyzing all the questions on the independent variables so that the hypothesis test results are obtained. If the results of the hypothesis test do not meet the eligibility index requirements. Then it needs to be analyzed by the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) method.

III. RESULT

Respondent Characteristic

Respondent characteristics are the characteristics of the respondents in this study. As for the characteristics of the respondents in this study include gender, age of the respondent, marital status, and the last education of the respondent. Based on the results of the study, the authors then identified the characteristics of the respondents as shown in Table 1. the following:

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

No.	Description	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Gender :		
	▪ Men	285	96,0
	▪ Women	12	4,0
Sum		297	100,0
2.	Age of respondent:		
	▪ 22 - 30 years	64	21,5
	▪ 31 - 40 years	152	51,2
	▪ 41 - 50 years	76	25,6
	▪ > 51 years	5	1,7
Sum		297	100,0
3.	Marital status		
	▪ Not Married	8	2,7
	▪ Married	289	97,3
Sum		297	100,0
4.	Education		
	▪ High school	0	0,0
	▪ Military Academy	248	83,5
	▪ Bachelor	39	13,1
	▪ Postgraduate	10	3,4
Sum		297	100,0

Source: Primary Data, 2019 (processed)

Based on the results of research on middle officers at the Kodam Iskandar Muda according to Table 1, this can be explained that as many as 285 people or 96.0% consisted of male respondents and as many as 12 people or 4.0% consisted of female respondents, thus the respondent members in the Kodam Iskandar Muda are dominated by male respondents, this is because military duties are mostly done by male respondents compared to female respondents.

Based on the age of the respondents it can be explained that as many as 64 people or 21.5% aged between 20 to 30 years were 152 people or 51.2% of respondents aged 30 to 40 years were 76 people or 25.6%, respondents aged 40 - 49 years and as many as 5 people or 1.7% of respondents aged over 50 years are not included in this study. Thus respondents with 30-40 years of age are more dominant than respondents aged 30-50 years are productive age levels who occupy many positions in the organizational structure at Kodam Iskandar Muda, so members have the maturity in thinking that has an impact on improving the performance of the Kodam Iskandar Muda organization.

Characteristics of respondents based on marital status can be explained that as many as 8 people or 2.7% of respondents were single, 289 people or 97.3% of respondents are married and those who were widowed / widowed 0 or 0.0%. Thus it can be explained that respondents who are married are more dominant than respondents who are not married.

Then the characteristics of the next respondent is regarding the education level of the respondent, it can be explained that as many as 248 people or 83.5% had the latest Military Academy education, as many as 39 people or 13.1% had the last Bachelor degree, while the respondents with the latest Postgraduate education are 10 people or 3.4 %, of the total respondents studied.

The results of the study based on the characteristics of respondents can be explained that the respondents in this study were dominated by male respondents compared to female respondents, then based on the age level, respondents aged 30-50 years were the dominant age level with married status. While the level of education, dominated by military-educated respondents, this is certainly intended to further enhance member competencies and member performance in the future.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

The latent variables of knowledge sharing and knowledge management system in this confirmatory model consist of 24 indicators as forming indicators. The results of data processing for confirmatory factor analysis for all constructs in this study are shown in the figure 1.

Figure 1. Constructive Confirmatory Factor Analysis

The loading factor that represents the contribution of each indicator to the variable it represents can be seen in the following table 2:

Table 2. Loading Factor

Indicator Code	Direction	Indicator	Estimate
ks1	<---	Knowledge_Sharing	0.563
ks2	<---	Knowledge_Sharing	0.765
ks3	<---	Knowledge_Sharing	0.510
ks4	<---	Knowledge_Sharing	0.586
ks5	<---	Knowledge_Sharing	0.860
ks6	<---	Knowledge_Sharing	0.960
ks7	<---	Knowledge_Sharing	0.953
ks8	<---	Knowledge_Sharing	0.789
pm1	<---	Knowledge Management	0.562
pm2	<---	Knowledge Management	0.658
pm3	<---	Knowledge Management	0.866
pm4	<---	Knowledge Management	0.629
ka1	<---	Member Competence	0.759
ka2	<---	Member Competence	0.764
ka3	<---	Member Competence	0.699
ka4	<---	Member Competence	0.655
ka5	<---	Member Competence	0.607
ka6	<---	Member Competence	0.653
kin1	<---	Member Performance	0.671
kin2	<---	Member Performance	0.896
kin3	<---	Member Performance	0.662

kin4	<---	Member Performance	0.672
kin5	<---	Member Performance	0.634
kin6	<---	Member Performance	0.628

Source: Primary Data, 2019 (processed)

Based on the table 2 above, it explains that all indicators included in the model have fulfilled the requirements to be included in the subsequent data processing. Before proceeding to the structural stage, the feasibility of the model will be seen first, this is because there are no indicators that have a value of less than 0.5. Testing the feasibility of the model is done by testing the model fit through goodness of fit.

Structural Equation Modeling Analysis

The next analysis is a full model Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis, after an analysis of the uni dimensionality level of the indicators forming latent variables was tested with confirmatory factor analysis. Analysis of the results of data processing at the full SEM model stage is carried out by conducting the suitability test and statistical test. The results of data processing for the full SEM model analysis are shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. Structural Equation Model (SEM) Test Result

This part explains the results of hypothesis testing as proposed in the previous chapter. The testing of 5 hypotheses of this study is carried out based on the Critical Ratio (CR) value of a causal relationship from the results of SEM processing as in table 3 below.

Table 3. Standardized Regression Weights

Endogen		Eksogen	Estimate	C.R.	P
Member Performance	<--	Knowledge Sharing	0.343	4.368	***
Member Performance	<--	Knowledge management	0.280	6.053	***
Member Competence	<--	Knowledge Sharing	0.250	3.068	***
Member Competence	---	Knowledge Management	0.174	3.220	***
Member Performance	<--	Member Competence	0.305	6.125	***

Source: Primary Data, 2019 (processed)

H1 is accepted

The estimated parameter for testing the effect of knowledge sharing on member performance shows a CR value of 4.368 and with a probability of 0.000. Both values are eligible for H1 acceptance, namely a CR value of 4.368 which is greater than 1.96 and a probability smaller than 0.05. Thus it can be concluded that the knowledge sharing owned by each member of the Kodam Iskandar Muda affects the performance of members. The magnitude of the influence of knowledge sharing on member performance amounted to 0.343.

H2 is accepted

The estimation parameter for testing the effect of knowledge management on member performance shows a CR value of 6.053 and with a probability of 0.000. Both values meet the requirements for H2 acceptance, namely a CR value of 6.053 which is greater than 1.96 and a probability smaller than 0.05. Thus it can be concluded that knowledge management owned by the Kodam Iskandar Muda affects the performance of the Kodam Iskandar Muda members. The magnitude of the influence of knowledge management on member performance amounted to 0.280.

H3 is accepted

The estimated parameter for testing the effect of knowledge sharing on member competence shows a CR value of 3.068 and with a probability of 0.000. Both of these values are obtained to meet the requirements for H4 acceptance, namely a CR value of 3.068 which is greater than 1.96 and a probability smaller than 0.05. Thus it can be concluded that knowledge sharing affects the competence of Kodam Iskandar Muda Members. Th

H4 is accepted

The estimated parameter for testing the effect of knowledge management on member performance shows a CR value of 3.220 and with a probability of 0.000. Both values are obtained to meet the requirements for acceptance of H5, namely a CR value of 3.220 which is greater than 1.96 and a probability smaller than 0.05. The magnitude of the influence of knowledge management on member competencies amounted to 0.174.

H5 is accepted

The estimated parameters for testing the effect of member competence on member performance shows a CR value of 6.125 and with a probability of 0.000. Both values meet the requirements for H2 acceptance, namely a CR value of 6.125 which is greater than 1.96 and a probability smaller than 0.05. Thus it can be concluded that the competency of the members owned by Kodam Iskandar Muda influence the performance of the Kodam Iskandar Muda members. The magnitude of the effect of member competence on member performance is 0.305.

H6 and H7 are rejected

Influence analysis is carried out to analyze the strength of influence between constructs, both direct, indirect and total influence. The coefficient and indirect effect results can be seen in the following table.

Table 4. Indirect effect

X	Y	Y	Z	X	Y	Z	z-Value (Sobel Test)
X ₁	Y(0.343)	Y	Z (0.305)	X ₁	Y	Z (0.076)	1.298
X ₂	Y(0.280)	Y	Z (0.305)	X ₁	Y	Z (0.053)	1.549
Ket: X1 = Knowledge Sharing X2 = Knowledge Management Y = Member Competence Z = Member Performance							

From the table 4 it figures Sobel Test result for indirect effect. Form the sobel test statistic z value, it shows the not eligible of H6 and H7 acceptances, both z value are 1.298 and 1.549 that are below 1.96. So the H6 is rejected and H7 is also rejected. So there is no indirect effect in this model that proven by the causality test.

Managerial implication

knowledge sharing has implications for increasing the competence of Kodam Iskandar Muda members, this is because having and obtaining knowledge from fellow members in order to increase the knowledge they have and increase insight in improving member performance, personal knowledge that they get from seniors can increase knowledge in carrying out tasks, then with knowledge sharing will also provide sharing of lessons that are considered difficult to solve with fellow colleagues especially in improving member competencies and improving member performance. Then with knowledge sharing can be an intermediary to achieve the needs of the organization and fellow members to share reports and documents that are considered important by each member. It also can share procedures in the organizational environment Kodam Iskandar Muda that is very necessary to create unity in the task so that it will be easy to achieve the expected performance by organization.

The knowledge management also has implications for increasing the competence of members and is also able to improve member performance. This shows from the use of members' knowledge that can provide benefits for the Kodam Iskandar Muda organization, then knowledge management can also be seen from sharing knowledge about leadership from each unit that can provide benefits for increasing the competence of members. this indicates that with knowledge management can provide good competence and increase the member performance. Knowledge management can also be seen from the reflection of knowledge carried out by each member. It can be a reference for improving the operational management of the organization and each member of the Kodam Iskandar Muda is able to identify any knowledge they receives, therefore by reflecting the knowledge and ability of members to identify each problems, so it will have an impact on improving member performance.

The implications related to member competencies on member performance can be seen from Kodam Iskandar Muda members having knowledge in accordance with their duties and functions, so that the existence of these tasks and functions will have an impact on improving the performance of members and they have skills in solving any problems that arise in the field. it has an impact on improving member performance. In this case based on the research model, member competence does not as a mediation variable that mediates the effect of knowledge sharing and knowledge management on member performance.

CONCLUSIONS

The result shows that knowledge sharing effects member performance significantly, knowledge management effects member performance significantly, knowledge sharing effects member competence significantly, knowledge management effects member competencies significantly, member competence effects member performance significantly, knowledge sharing does not effect member performance through member competence, and knowledge management does not effect member performance through member competence. These findings support the realm of science that prove the causality theories. The originality rests in the collaboration of the previous models, and in using SEM as a statistical approach to test the effect among variables. The limitation resides in the number of variables and object. These results also impact to the practical leaders especially in the Kodam Iskandar Muda as an object. To improve the performance of members, the Kodam Iskandar Muda leaders need to formulate the policies related to the knowledge

sharing and knowledge management so the members have a willingness to share their knowledge to their colleagues, and the organization has the knowledge management to provide the knowledge and skills of members in accordance with their duties and functions.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Azmi, I. N., Nasir and Sofyan (2019) 'The Effect of Organizational Commitment and its Implications on Employee Performance in the Dental Hospital and Mouth of Universitas Syiah Kuala Banda Aceh', *International Journal of Social Science & Economic Research*, 4(9).
- [2.] Davidson, C. and Voss, P. (2002) *Knowledge Management: An Introduction to Creating Competitive Advantage from Intellectual Capital*. USA: Tandem Press.
- [3.] Diana, M. M. (2009) 'Pengaruh Knowledge Management dan Kompetensi terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan', *manajerial*, 7(14).
- [4.] F. Hair Jr, J. et al. (2014) 'Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) An emerging tool in business research', *European Business Review*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited, 26(2), pp. 106-121.
- [5.] Flippo, E. B. (1997) *Manajemen personalia*. Edited by (Alih bahasa: Mohd Mas'ud). Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [6.] Hartati, I. (2005) 'Pengaruh Kesesuaian Kompetensi dan Motivasi Kerja terhadap Kinerja Pegawai pada Sekretariat Daerah Kabupaten Malang', *Jurnal Eksekutif*, 2(1), pp. 63-80.
- [7.] Mahfud, Y. (2016) 'Pengaruh Knowledge Management, Skill, Dan Attitude Terhadap Employee Performance (Studi Kasus Pada DPPKAD Kabupaten Banjarnegara)', *Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Manajemen dan Akuntansi*, 12(1), pp. 49-81.
- [8.] Mangkunegara, A. A. A. P. (2010) *Evaluasi Kinerja SDM*. 2nd edn. Bandung: Refika Aditama.
- [9.] Robbins, S. P. and Judge, T. A. (2012) *Organizational Behavior*. 15th edn. Edited by S. Yagan. San Diego: Pearson.
- [10.] Salda, I., Faisal and Majid, M. S. A. (2019) 'Effect of Competence, Motivation, Organizational Climate, and Organizational Culture on Teachers' Performance of the Public High Schools: Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction', *East African Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 2(9).
- [11.] Suprihanto, J. (1987) *Penilaian Pelaksanaan Pekerjaan dan pengembangan Karyawan*. Yogyakarta: BPFE.
- [12.] Susanto, D. B., Faisal and Putra, T. R. I. (2019) 'The Effect Of Knowledge Management, Organizational Learning And Work Satisfaction Toward Organizational Commitment And Its Impact On Employee Performance In Sekretariat Office, District Of Nagan Raya, Aceh Province, Indonesia', *International Journal of Social Science and Economic Research*, (7), pp. 5066-5076.
- [13.] Timpe, A. D. (2002) *Seri Ilmu dan seni Manajemen Bisnis (Memimpin Manusia)*. Jakarta: Gramedia.
- [14.] Trivellas, P. et al. (2015) 'The Impact of Knowledge Sharing Culture on Job Satisfaction in Accounting Firms. The Mediating Effect of General Competencies', *Procedia Economics and Finance*. Elsevier B.V., 19(15), pp. 238-247. doi: 10.1016/s2212-5671(15)00025-8.
- [15.] Waldman, D. A. and Siegel, D. (2008) 'Defining the socially responsible leader', *Leadership Quarterly*, 19(1), pp. 117-131. doi: 10.1016/j.leaqua.2007.12.008.
- [16.] Wibowo (2016) *Manajemen Kinerja*. kelima. Jakarta: PT. Rajagrafindo Persada.
- [17.] Wijayanto, B. R. and Kismono, G. (2004) 'The Effect Of Job Embeddedness On Organizational Citizenship Behavior: The Mediating Role Of Sense Of Responsibility', *Gadjah Mada International Journal of Business*, 4(3), pp. 335-354. doi: <https://doi.org/10.22146/gamajib.5554>.
- [18.] Yazhou, W. and Jian, L. I. N. (2013) 'An empirical research on knowledge management orientation and organizational performance: the mediating role of organizational innovation', *African Journal of Business Management*, 7(8), pp. 604-612. doi: 10.5897/AJBM11.2072.